

Deliverable 2.6

DATA EXCHANGE SYSTEM FOR CREATING AND MANAGING IDENTITIES AND CREDENTIALS RELATED TO FEDERATED RESEARCH PROJECTS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides a high-level overview of the identity and credential management system developed under Work Package 2. Identities, credentials and their use cases are presented together with trust required between actors in PHEMS federated network. Both current implementation and future possibilities offered by decentralized identity and credential management are considered.

NOTE: This deliverable was originally named “Data exchange system for creating verifiable data access requests” in the Grant Agreement. The name was later changed to more accurately reflect the identified needs and developed functionalities.

1. Introduction

The primary objective of Work Package 2 (WP2) is to establish a federated network connecting the four data controllers within the consortium. This network enables data users, including researchers, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and other innovators, to perform analytics and federated learning tasks on OMOP-modeled datasets, which remain under the control of their respective data controllers. By supporting distributed data analysis, the network fosters collaborative research while maintaining data privacy and security.

Task 2.5 is dedicated to developing tools that allow data users to request access to cohort data across distributed OMOP databases. In parallel, Task 2.4 provides functionalities for browsing and defining cohorts tailored to the specific requirements of data users.

To meet these objectives there must be a way to manage identities and credentials used inside the federated network to ensure that users are who they claim to be, and that they can only access information that is included in the permissions that they possess. For identity and credential management, the plan is to utilize decentralized identity where applicable.

2. Glossary

Table 1 ABBREVIATIONS	
TERM	DESCRIPTION
WP	Work Package
PHDS	Pediatric Health Data Space
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (common data model for health data)
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
App	Application
IAM	Identity and access management
DID	Decentralized identity

Table 2 TERMS AND DEFINITIONS	
TERM	DESCRIPTION
Data Controller	An organization or institution within the consortium that determines the purposes and means for processing personal data, in accordance with applicable regulations.
Data User	A person or entity, such as a researcher, SME, or innovator, who requests access to data for the purpose of conducting analytics, research, or other approved activities.
Permit App	A user-friendly software tool designed to facilitate the management of federated analytics and learning projects, as well as the submission and review of data permit applications.
Cohort	A group of individuals or data subjects identified based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria, typically defined using the OMOP common data model.
Cohort Definition	A formal specification outlining the characteristics and parameters used to select a cohort from the available datasets.
Data Permit	Official approval issued by a data controller, granting a data user permission to access and utilize a specified cohort for research or analytical purposes.
Pre-study	A preliminary assessment was conducted to confirm that sufficient and relevant data exists within the network to support the intended research on a defined cohort.
Federated Learning	A collaborative machine learning technique in which models are trained across multiple decentralized data sources, ensuring that raw data remains local, and privacy is preserved.

3. System architecture

Figure 1. Technical architecture of the identity and credential management system.

The technical architecture shows the key parties, actors, and credentials they need to access various resources in the system. Some of these credentials are held by the users while some are stored in key stores for automation to use.

Researchers have an option to use a decentralized identity, as defined by the W3C organization, that is attested by a trusted third party. PHDS access providers can then assign roles to this identity, and data controllers can associate with it permits and access permissions they grant.

The members of the network can issue their own credentials for the identities, and they can trust credentials issued by each other, forming trust relationships within the network.

Federated nodes use their own credentials to retrieve containers (workloads) that they run, and the containers use data controllers' credentials to Shared Services to publish results. They sign their results with a container-specific key that is created at build time, which binds the container and its results together. Information about the environment (e.g. which DC provided the results) is included in the package and signed also.

4. PHDS identities and credentials

The PHDS network contains multiple types of entities which must be uniquely identifiable. Each entity can be assigned some kind of proof of digital identity, or a credential, that is created by a PHDS network participant and is verifiable by other PHDS participants.

This chapter gives an overview of different identities and their identification mechanisms. The table below defines each entity which has a digital identity, which participant is responsible for creating the identity, and which system is used to verify it (anchoring method).

Entity	Identity anchored by	Identity anchoring method
PHDS access provider	PHDS Governance entity	PHDS Trust Registry
Data Controller	PHDS Governance entity	PHDS Trust Registry
Researcher / Data User / Project member	PHDS access provider	PHDS access provider's IAM + IDV service
Project	PHDS access provider	PHDS access provider's IAM
Data Controller's Employee (optional)	Data Controller	Data Controller's IAM

Table 1. PHDS identities and anchoring methods

Each digital identity in PHDS can be associated with a Decentralized Identifier (DID), which is used by the ecosystem members to verify the entity's digital signatures and credentials issued by them or for them. Where technology doesn't yet enable using DIDs, other types of identity verifications can be used. This doesn't change the division of responsibilities.

4.1. PHDS Trust Registry

The PHDS Trust Registry includes all the PHDS access providers and data controllers of the ecosystem. When DIDs are used, another PHDS ecosystem member may query the registry and retrieve identity information required to verify the issued credentials. The PHDS Governance entity is the authority to assert the status of the member agreement. If we consider a more traditional Public Key Infrastructure, the trust registry would act as a root of trust; however, this Proof-of-Concept implementation aims at using DIDs to achieve the same outcome.

The same real-life entity may act as several entities in the network.

Example:

The Helsinki University Hospital (HUS) acts in both the Data Controller and PHDS access provider roles. As HUS has active agreements for both roles, they will have two Decentralized Identifiers:

Data Controller: `did:web:phds.example.com:dc:hus`

PHDS access provider: `did:web:phds.example.com:wp:hus`

Each entry will contain the following type of information from the PHDS trust registry. Using the cryptographic key information, the participants can verify the signatures made by the HUS in each of its roles respectively.

```
{
  "@context": [
    "https://www.w3.org/ns/did/v1",
    https://w3id.org/security/suites/jws-2020/v1
  ],
  "id": "did:web:phds.example.com:dc:hus",
  "verificationMethod": [
    {
      "id": "did:web:phds.example.com:dc:hus#key-1",
      "type": "JsonWebKey2020",
      "publicKeyJwk": {
        "kty": "OKP",
        "crv": "Ed25519",
        "x": "0-e2i2_Ua1S5HbTYnVB0lj2Z2ytXu2-tYmDFf8f5NjU"
      }
    },
    {
      "id": "did:web:phds.example.com:dc:hus#key-2",
      "type": "JsonWebKey2020",
      "publicKeyJwk": {
        "kty": "OKP",
        "crv": "X25519",
        "x": "9GXjPGGvmRq9F6Ng5dQQ_s31mfhxrcNZxRGONrmH30k"
      }
    }
  ],
  "assertionMethod": [
    "did:web:example.com#key-1",
    "did:web:example.com#key-2"
  ]
}
```

4.2. Credentials

PHDS uses standardized digital credentials as a mechanism to prove authorizations or approvals. For example, credentials are issued to prove that a data permit, cohort, and code have been approved by a data controller, or that a data user is authorized to participate in a project.

The credentials are digitally signed by the issuing entity, using secret keys available only to that entity. Credentials can be verified by anyone who has access to them. The verification includes validating

the binding between the credentials, and the entity or object to ensure non-repudiation or fraudulent credential issuance. Use of credentials creates a security layer on top of the data exchange, to ensure that if data exchange or collaboration layer is compromised, the critical data remains verifiable and uncompromised.

The table below lists the primary credentials used in the network. More credential types can be later defined in the implementation guides.

Credential	Issued by	Purpose	Entity / Object
User identity	PHDS Governance Entity	To verify the identity of a researcher / user / project member	Users in the network
Project Information	PHDS access Provider	To verify that the project is valid and only approved members have access to the project.	Project + project members
Data permit	Data Controllers	To verify that the data permit application has been approved, and a data permit has been issued by the data controller. The data permit credential includes verification of the data permit application, code, and cohort.	Data Permit, including the approved data permit application content and the cohort definition.

Table 2. PHDS Credentials

5. Technical framework and standards

5.1. Decentralized identities

DID is a string that follows certain convention. `did:method:method-specific-identifier` This DID is a pointer to a DID document, which tells more about the person or other entity the DID is pointing to. The DID itself does not contain any personally identifiable information (PII) so it can be shared with anyone or made publicly accessible.

It can be associated with other information. For example, it could be stored in shared services database as part of the data permit applications. It could be also shared via a QR code, email, business card, etc.

The DID document can be obtained from the location described in DID through a method specific DID Resolver. It might look like `did:web:example.com:users:userid`

Resolving the DID results in <https://example.com/users/userid/.well-known/did.json> and from that location a DID document can be found. The contents of the DID Document may look like the following:

```
{
  ...
  "id": "did:web:example.com:users:alice",
  "verificationMethod": [{
    "id": " did:web:example.com:users:alice ",
    "type": "Ed25519VerificationKey2018",
    "controller": " did:web:example.com:users:alice ",
    "publicKeyBase58": "H3C2AVvLM8Th3..."
  }]
}
```

With this information we can establish that the person pointed at in the DID (DID points to a DID Document which describes the person and his associated public key) owns the respective private key.

At this point we don't necessarily know anything about the person, but we can know that once the identity is verified, and assuming the private key is kept secure, in future interactions we are always dealing with the same person.

How to connect the DID Document and associated keys with an identity? There are a few potential ways, including:

1. The person's DID Document can be verified by each party separately, which establishes trust with one party at a time. The public key can be stored for future reference along with other required information about the person.
2. The web site where the DID Document is made available can be assumed secure and registering a new user follows a process where the identity is verified. In this case the information about the person is retrieved from the web site and the fact that the person offering a certain DID can prove he owns the private key matching the public key in DID Document. This can happen e.g. by signing a challenge the party which is requesting an identification sends.
3. Verifiable credentials which outsource the verification to a trusted third party in well-defined manner. We will cover this later in this document.

DIDs are scalable way to establish identities. They enable a full identity sovereignty and full decentralization in principle, but at this point we will aim at enterprise style system where we have some trusted parties that the others can rely on, because this is more cost-effective and makes it easier for the parties to establish trust. Full decentralization is still technically an option, so this is more a rule book matter.

5.2. Verifiable credentials

Verifiable credentials add an extra level of indirection to identification and authorization process, which makes it more efficient at the expense of having to trust to someone else. With verifiable credentials we have a trusted third-party attest something about a person. In other words, a trusted third party can confirm certain information about a person. This could be e.g. a proof that they have already

verified the identity of a person, or it could be a proof of participation in a certain project, or proof of being a principal investigator of that project, or anything that is considered useful. Based on that attestation others can grant the person accesses and privileges, because someone else has already established who they are and what their role in the project is.

6. Identity and credential use cases in PHEMS project

To showcase what can be achieved with decentralised identities and verifiable credentials, the Work Package 2 has produced a tool for managing data permit applications called the Permit App. The tool uses Verifiable Credentials to identify the users. To support these uses cases, WP2 has also implemented an identity proofer system that enables the participants to prove their identities and obtain verifiable credentials that can be then presented to the Permit App for onboarding and logging in. This system is currently based on Microsoft Entra ID, but any other IAM system that supports DIDs and VC according to standards could be used.

6.1. Issuance of a Verifiable Credential for an identity

The diagram below (figure 2.) illustrates the identification process with a decentralized identity system using an identity proofer that the other parties in the PHDS network trust. In the proof of concept, the identity proofer is a custom application, but it can be a trusted 3rd party (as in the diagrams), or it could be a role that is assigned to e.g. the PHDS access provider, some hospitals or some universities. The identity proofer verifies the person's real-world identity and issues a Verifiable Credential that contains attestations about the person's identity, signed by the identity proofer. This Verifiable Credential is stored in the digital wallet of the researchers and can be used for proving the identity to those who trust the identity proofer.

Figure 2. The identification process with a decentralized identity system using an identity proofer that the other parties in the PHDS network trust.

The following picture (figure 3) shows how issuance of a verifiable credential might look from the researcher’s perspective.

The researcher initiates the issuance by going to the identity proofer’s web site (or office if physical presence is required, or bureau if the Identity Proofer is a government). In this case a web site is assumed, and the researcher uses a mobile phone which contains a secure environment, a digital wallet, for holding the identity and credentials.

The researcher starts the process by using their mobile phone to scan a QR code on the Identity Proofer’s web site. In the case of the Permit App, the Identity Proofer is a custom application running as an App Service in Microsoft Azure and the researcher’s identity has already been checked by the time the QR code is presented – in practice when the researcher’s identity was created in the Entra ID.

The process would be very similar in a physical location where the identity could be checked using an official document (e.g. a passport) and then the issuance of a credential is initiated through scanning a QR code.

Figure 3. How issuance of a verifiable credential might look from the researcher's perspective.

The issued credential is stored in the user's digital wallet. Microsoft Authenticator can act as a digital wallet, for example.

6.2. Presentation of a verifiable credential during login

In the next diagram (figure 4.), the researcher has a project created for them (or alternatively directed to an existing project) after identification. The Permit App assigns roles for the researchers and can store identity-role-mapping in an internal database, or alternatively it could issue a verifiable credential of its own that the researcher can use in the future to authenticate.

It is assumed here that the researcher has obtained a verifiable credential and thus can prove their identity when they start onboarding to a project. The process could also start with onboarding, and if an identity credential doesn't exist yet, the Permit App redirects the researcher to perform the identity proofing with a trusted third party before coming back and continuing onboarding to a project.

The diagram shows a researcher requesting a new project. The verifier (Permit App) requests proof of identity, and the researcher proves that by sending a verifiable presentation back. The verifier checks that the credential is valid (this step could be omitted with short-living credentials if network traffic were to be minimized) and once the identity is verified, then the researcher can provide information about the project.

Figure 4.

Handling the data permit application through Shared Services enables connecting the permits and projects together seamlessly and enables a simpler implementation for permit handling regardless of the number of Permit App instances running. When the researcher wants to use an issued verifiable credential, the presentation starts the same way as issuance, by scanning a QR code.

It might look like as follows:

Figure 5.

After scanning the code with a mobile device, the user confirms if he allows the sharing of the credential with the verifier.

Approving this passes the attestations in the credential to the verifier who can then map the identity contained in those to the data they have about the person, for example, their roles. Before accepting attestations, the verifier may want to check with the Identity Proofer that the credential has not been revoked, and the attestations are signed by a party the verifier trusts.

The process of verifying the identity is similar whether it is started by the Permit App, PHDS access provider, or a Data Controller: The verifier challenges the person controlling the DID to prove their identity and after the person approves presenting the credential, the verifier gets back a verifiable presentation containing attestations about the identity signed a trusted party they trust.

6.3. Requesting presentation of a verifiable credential before approving the data permit application

The following diagram shows how a data permit application is filled out and submitted, a process which is described in detail in deliverable 2.5. A globally unique identifier is stored along with the application, or alternatively a DID could be used here, too. This enables the data controller to find out the real-world identity of the people (if they so choose) and then assign their own permissions and other related metadata to them. When using DIDs, the data controller is expected to trust the identity proofer of the network, but they could also perform the identification by themselves and issue a verifiable credential of their own. Such a self-issued Verifiable Credential would then be stored in the researcher's digital wallet along with the other credentials.

The following diagram shows a scenario where the data controller is reading the DID, which acts as a unique identifier, and then challenges the researcher to prove their identity directly. This part has not been implemented at the time of writing this, so currently the identity verification must be done outside the application, but it is possible to implement that in the future and as drawn in the diagram, it shows the flexibility of a decentralized identity system.

Interoperability between multiple trust domains is outside of the scope of this project, so to release the full potential of decentralized identities, gathering every entity under a single trust domain is encouraged. The system can work also with multiple trust domains, however, but it may lead to a proliferation of verifiable credentials and that may become tricky to manage because of varying issuers and expiration times.

Figure 6. How a data permit application is filled out and submitted, a process which is described in detail in deliverable 2.5.

7. Future Possibilities of Decentralized Identity and Verifiable Credentials

DIDs can be associated with other entities, too, not only humans. This requires a key store where the private key can be held and some person (or perhaps an automated process) which is considered the controller of that key. One way to use verifiable credentials in the context of this project is to grant a container a permission to run through those. The container can be given an identity, and the controller of the identity can request a verifiable credential, which is then granted by a party that the container runtime environment trusts. Before issuing a verifiable credential, the issuer has already verified that the code is acceptable, and the container is built securely. Then that container can be run even without further checkpoints.

This enables flexible relationships between the identities (of containers), issuers of credentials and verifiers (run-time environments). Some run-time environments may trust a particular issuer, another set of issuers, another requires any set of issuers plus one issued by a security team, and someone may want to issue every credential by themselves, so they trust no-one else.

But there can be more things to verify beyond identity. They can issue their own credentials that attest that the person is associated with a particular project in a particular organization (university in this case, and every data controller may trust the university issued credential), or if they want to do checks by themselves, the person has been evaluated by a data controller and the data controller has

checked the identity (whichever way they consider sufficient) and accepted that the person may be in the project.

Results are an entity, too. A particular set of results can be associated with an identity. The identity can be associated with that of the container that generated the results.

A DID is created for this set of data, and that DID is published along with the data to Shared Services. The DID document contains a hash of data and relevant metadata. A trusted party issues a verifiable credential to the identity of the data, and in that credential, it includes attestations. Attestations can tell where the data can be published.

The following diagram shows how the credentials can be issued and utilized. In the diagram the Identity Proofer verifies the researcher’s identity and issues a verifiable credential that contains attestations about the identity. The other members of the network are expected to trust the Identity Proofer (it may be e.g. a government) and so they don’t have to go through identity verification again.

There can be trust relationships between the data controllers, too. In diagram the data controller 3 trusts the data controller 1, and data controllers 4 and 5 trust the data controller 2. This means that it is enough for the data controllers 1 and 2 to verify the researcher’s identity and participation in the project, and the rest of the network accepts the credentials issued by these data controllers and they can avoid having to check the identity and the project participation by themselves. Such trust relationships may emerge in the network over time.

Figure 7. Various sources of verifiable credentials and how a potential trust network could form.

8. Conclusions

The demonstration of identity and credential management highlights its effectiveness in supporting decentralized federated analysis and learning scenarios. By providing a simple and secure way of managing identities of researchers and credentials they possess, the system enhances collaboration between data users and data controllers, streamlines the permit application process, and ensures compliance with regulatory requirements. The functionalities described in this deliverable contribute to the overall objectives of the project, fostering innovation and responsible data use within the federation network.